

D10.7 Final Data Management Plan

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2	12/03/2024	Sergio Jiménez (CIMNE)	Revision according to PO specifications and resubmission

Executive summary

Fatigue4Light's main objective is to rely on the vehicle parts selected to address the lightweighting efforts, the vehicle chassis, as the most effective approach to maximize the impact of the developed material solutions. They can be deployed to all the range of electrical vehicles, from battery electric vehicles (BEVs) to hybrid (HEVs) and plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs). Fatigue4Light uses advanced numerical simulation tools and experimental techniques to assure part performance and reduce the lead times for the market introduction of new light and high-performance chassis parts. Fatigue4Light material solutions are developed from an eco-design perspective, with clear environmental gain in terms of energy use and cradle-to-cradle perspective at affordable cost and considering critical raw materials availability.

Fatigue4Light aims to develop lightweight solutions adapted to the chassis part of EV to reach a 24-30% weight reduction, which will give a 12-15% weight savings from structural vehicle weight, and also increase EV safety due to reduced sprung mass. Solutions will be based on the introduction of specially developed materials solutions with high fatigue performance (AHSS, stainless steel, Al alloys and hybrid metal-FRP materials), the development of new computer modelling with high fatigue prediction accuracy and new experimental methodologies that reduce the testing time for new materials. Affordability including critical raw materials for EU assessment, and sustainability of the proposed solutions, will be enhanced based on the application of an eco-design approach supported by the application of LCA and LCC studies.

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes data to be collected within the Fatigue4Light project, and the data management methods. The DMP includes a description of methodology and standards to be followed and what data sets are exploitable or made accessible for verification and re-use. Additionally, this document pools the results generated in the project that may lead to intellectual property (IP), thus acting as a mechanism for innovation management. The DMP will thus contain all forms of knowledge generated by the project. The DMP will be a dynamic tool that is updated regularly when changes are required.

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List of abbreviations

<i>BEVs</i>	<i>Battery Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>DMP</i>	<i>Data Management Plan</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>HEVs</i>	<i>Hybrid Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>LDV</i>	<i>Light-Duty Vehicles</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

Introduction

The Data Management Plan encompasses key facets of ensuring data is FAIR – findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. This involves specifying the data generated by the project, its accessibility for verification and reuse, and the methods for curation and preservation. This deliverable presents the final version of the Data Management Plan for the Fatigue4Light Project.

As stipulated in the Grant Agreement, the project’s DMP outlines the nature of data generated, its potential use or accessibility for verification and reuse, and the strategies for storage and preservation. Fatigue4Light stated in the Grant Agreement that it would follow the FAIR Data management guidelines in H2020.

This deliverable presents all the process and the efforts that have been made during the project in order to ensure that Fatigue4Light’s data follows the FAIR principles This document is structured in two main section:

- **The Data Management Plan itself**, which is based in the guidelines for H2020 Data Management provided by the European Commission
- The presentation of the **data collected** during the project, which includes:
 - **WP:** Work Package involved.
 - **Data collected or created:** whether the data has been created during the project or collected based on other sources.
 - **Title:** general descriptive name of the dataset
 - **Description:** brief explanation of the data and relation to the project objectives
 - **Category:** category of the data, as stated in the Grant Agreement:
 - Research data and metadata: datasets resulting from research on materials and manufacturing processes; metadata and configuration files; bug logs and feedback logs; developer internal documentation; market research.
 - Computer software: including software applications, libraries in the form of SDKs, plugins and respective source code
 - Data for evaluation: consists of materials or datasets generated or collected by the project for evaluation purposes
 - Documents and dissemination materials: Includes deliverables, reports, demonstrations, dissemination and communication.
 - **Date of creation**
 - **Creator:** Partner responsible for the creation of the data
 - **Contributors:** relevant contributors besides the main creator
 - **File location:** where is the data located.
 - **Software** used to create the data.
 - **Expected size** of the data
 - **Means for OA:** how is public data going to be published in Open Access
 - **Related KER:** related Key Exploitable Results

- **Privacy level:** whether the Data is considered Public or Confidential
- **Confidentiality reason:** if Data is considered Confidential, reasons on why it is
- **Confidentiality duration:** how long data will be confidential

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time and content deviation.

Data summary

The main goal of Fatigue4Light is to investigate lightweight solutions adapted to the chassis part of Electric Vehicles to reach a 24-30% weight reduction. The Data Management Plan compiles and collects all the data generated in the Fatigue4Light project during the process of achieving the goals of each Work Package:

WP Number	WP Title
WP1	Eco-design of lightweight materials
WP2	New approach for fatigue evaluation
WP3	Fatigue modelling
WP4	Effect of manufacturing on fatigue
WP5	Part performance monitoring
WP6	Long-life Eco-design for EVs
WP7	Lightweighting EV chassis parts
WP8	New tools to assess optimal weight savings and performance
WP9	Coordination
WP10	Dissemination & exploitation

The main types of data that have been developed during the projects are:

- Simulation and feasibility data
- Material and testing data
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and environmental data
- Modeling and documentation
- Sensors and Health monitoring
- Reports and deliverables
- Standardization and dissemination

The main formats by which these data have been worked with are:

- .psp
- .xlsx
- .docx
- .pptx
- .pdf
- .st7

- .prt
- .db
- .txt
- .json
- .mdpa
- .post.bin
- .e3
- .k

Fatigue4Light involves the reuse of existing data, such as compilation of existing literature relevant to the project objectives and a summary of existing software solutions applicable to the project.

The data compiled in the project originates from various sources, including:

- Simulation and testing: data generated through simulations, feasibility studies, and experimental tests conducted within the project.
- Literature and meetings: information gathered from existing literature and project meetings.
- External sources: existing data and software solutions sourced externally and adapted for project purposes.

The data has been obtained through active collaboration with all the Partners and a regular update throughout the whole project, actively updating the data repository of the project every 6 months.

The expected size of the data varies depending on the type. However, most of the data range between small (less than 10MB) and moderate-sized (less than 1GB) with some bigger size exceptionalities.

The data generated will be useful to:

- Project Partners: for internal analyses, development, and collaboration on lightweight solutions.
- Academic and research communities: providing valuable insights for further research in lightweight materials and fatigue resistance.
- Industry professionals: offering practical solutions, simulation models, and best practices.

Making data findable

Metadata is typically presented as structured textual information, describing aspects of a digital resource's origin, content, or context, whether it pertains to a singular file, a segment within a file, or an assortment of multiple files. Serving as a crucial tool, metadata facilitates the discovery, management, description, preservation and establishment of relationships with and between digital resources.

Fatigue4Life will tackle the generation of metadata and adherence to standards by depositing its non-confidential data into Zenodo. Specifically, Zenodo

generates accompanying metadata for the datasets uploaded to its repository, broadening the reach to a diverse audience of stakeholders. This metadata is exportable in various standard formats, including open and machine-readable ones, aligning with the guidelines set by OpenAIRE.

For disseminating data to a broader audience, persistent identifier/references will be employed, exemplified by a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) number from the International DOI Foundation assigned to a publication, As outlined in the Grant Agreement for the project, the commitment is made to explore the utilization of online and open services, aligning with the FAIR policy, and leveraging OPENAIRE-compliant repositories such as Zenodo. Zenodo systematically assigns DOIs to all submitted data, ensuring prolonged accessibility and serving as enduring links to resources. Consequently, these DOIs enhances the discoverability of the project results for third parties. In addition to this, while non-confidential data may also be uploaded to the Fatigue4Light's webpage in certain instances, it's important to note that long-term preservation is not guaranteed in these latter cases.

To facilitate all the data management process, the naming convention that has been recommended to the Partners is:

F4L_[Study name]_[Dataset number]_[Modification Date]_[Version number]

- F4L: Abbreviation of the project (Fatigue4Life)
- Study name: description of the activity for which the dataset is generated
- Dataset number: An identifier assigned to the dataset
- Modification Date: The date when the most recent version of the dataset was updated (YYY.MM.DD)
- Version number: The version number associated with the dataset

Appropriate search keywords are applied to each dataset to enhance the discoverability for potential users. Typically, keywords, which constitute a subset of metadata, consist of words employed to label data. Within the framework of Fatigue4Light, these keywords serve the dual purpose of augmenting the information associated with the collected data and streamlining the description of its content. The keywords will be terms such as Fatigue, Modelling, Chassis, Lightweight, Testing, LCA, Ecodesign, etc.

The process of versioning information provides a distinctive identification datasets and serves to ascertain the nature and extent of changes in the data over time. It also aids in specifying the particular version that the creators or the editors are currently handling. Each version is differentiated, as previously seen, by a version number and a date.

In the case of datasets related to deliverables, the versioning number follows a specific format, consisting of two digits separated by a period. The digit preceding the period indicates the official versions submitted to the European Commission.

The digits following the period denote the periodic internal revisions made to these official versions. (e.g. 1.1 / 1.2/ 2.1/2.2...)

Datasets that are not deliverables will be identified by a version number in the file name consisting in a “v” followed by a number: v001 / v002 / v003...

After a careful review, during the updating process, older versions that are considered to not be useful anymore will be deleted.

The main metadata that will be created in the project will be technical and operational, as it can be appreciated in the list of generated data.

Making data openly accessible

Fatigue4Light will make an active effort to make all the generated data available for open access under the FAIR principles. By default, all data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available except in three different situations, as stated in the Grant Agreement:

- Confidentiality and IP protection to certain deliverables, datasets and outputs
- Any sensitive or personal data collected during the project will be dealt with in compliance with Directive 95/46/EC and GDPR Regulation 2016/679, considering consent, breach notification, right to access and right to be forgotten.
- Protection of imported rights of pre-existent, non-public datasets

If any of these three situations apply, but nonetheless all related partners agree to make related data public, the project will proceed to do so.

As stated before, data will be made accessible by using OPENAIRE compliant repositories (ZENODO, GitHub...), and it will be made sure that it is covered by a machine readable license (CC BY 4.0 DEED). Also, data related to public deliverables and presentations will be made available in the Fatigue4Light website (<https://fatigue4light.eu/>). Methods to access the data, such as specific software, will be specified. Relevant software that has been used and that is already publicly available will be stated.

There will not be restrictions on use of published data. There is no need for a data access committee as confidential data will not be published at all and the rest is going to be openly accessible in free data repositories. There is no need to ascertain the identity of the person accessing the data since it will be made publicly available.

Making data interoperable.

Data adheres to prevalent standards for formats, aiming to maximize its interoperability. The Consortium aims at facilitating its seamless exchange and reuse among researchers, institutions, and organizations, especially allowing and facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins.

To achieve interoperability, the Consortium will adhere to established data and metadata vocabularies, standards, and methodologies. This involves adopting common conventions and structures that are widely recognized and accepted within the relevant scientific or research community.

In terms of standard vocabularies, for each data type present in our dataset, the Consortium will use well-recognized and widely accepted terminologies and classifications. This approach will allow researchers from various disciplines to understand and use the data effectively, promoting interdisciplinary interoperability.

Increasing data re-use

Published data in Zenodo will be licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0 DEED) in order to ensure public data generated during the project is made available for any purpose, and making anyone free to use, reuse, and distribute it, while also giving appropriate credit to the Partner(s) responsible for generating the data.

Public data will be made available for re-use in the next 3 months after the end of the project. Confidential data related to exploitable result susceptible to be covered by an IPR strategy will have a data embargo of 10 years to provide enough time to the Partners to publish or seek this IPR strategy.

As stated in this document, public data generated during Fatigue4Light will be useable for third parties after the end of the project, only forbidding its re-usability in the case that the data is labeled as confidential for the following reasons:

- Data related to confidential deliverables, as agreed with the European Commission
- Data related to exploitable results susceptible to be protected by an Intellectual Property Rights strategy (patent, copyright, etc.)
- Data owned by a Partner and not generated during the project.

Public data aims at remains re-usable for as long as possible. After publishing it in the public repository, no effort will be made in the future to retire it.

To ensure data quality, Partners will be entirely responsible for the data they generate, while the Project Coordinator also applies a review process before making the data public.

Allocation of resources

The activities involved in processing, storing and documenting the data are allocated within each Partner's budget for respective work packages and contribute to the overall project budget. The expenses associated with making the data FAIR are accounted for in Task 10.3 "Exploitation Activities", in accordance with the terms outlined in the Grant Agreement. As stated, as data will be made available in public repositories, no extra costs are expected.

Concerning the website, its costs are budgeted for a duration of three years post-project to ensure sustained functionality. It is not expected to keep it after these three years. Nevertheless, all pertinent, non-confidential data generated in the project will also undergo preservation through the Zenodo repository, as stated in this document.

Data Security

Throughout the project, access to datasets has been restricted to accredited Partners whose data usage has received approval from either the Coordinator or an authorized Partner. Fatigue4Light has stored sensitive data in both Partners' servers and encrypted common spaces (Sharepoint), not accessible for those who were not approved by the Coordinator.

As stated, public data will be stored in Zenodo, a repository that ensures data security. Confidential data will remain in Partners' servers and in the common space established by Fatigue4Light. Partners, in collaboration with the coordinator, are entrusted with the responsibility of appropriately managing, safeguarding, sharing, and removing their confidential datasets.

Ethical aspects

In handling personal data, Fatigue4Light ensures strict adherence to Article 39 of the General Assembly and EU Regulation 201/679 on personal data protection. The commitment is upheld through the execution of data checks. The Consortium affirm their compliance with the EU GDPR, encompassing pertinent systems and privacy protocols. They incorporate privacy-by-design and privacy-by-default principles and pledge to implement technical and organizational measures in line with GDPR requirements.

Fatigue4Light is not designed to collect or handle sensitive personal data, such as information pertaining to religion, health, ethnicity, etc. Specifically, in the context of social media analysis, Partners commit to avoiding the collection of private personal information, including sensitive data, and refrain from employing covert methods to access social media data.

Partners have reviewed all data that is going to be shared publicly and fully agree with the process, including its long term preservation. Partners have been instructed on how to accomplish requirements regarding data management by Fatigue4Light's Data Manager.

Fatigue4Light Data

WP	Data collected or created	Title	Description and relation to the project objectives	Category	Data of creation	Creator	Contributors	File location	File format	Software used to create data	Expected size of data	Related KER	Privacy level	Confidentiality reason	Confidentiality duration	Means for OA
WP1	Created	Prefeasibility stamping simulations	Prefeasibility of disc stamping with proposed steel grades	Research data and metadata	M1-6	MW	Arcelor Mittal (material cards)	Partner server	.psp (and related process files .asw, .att, .res, .his, etc.)	ESI pam-stamp	10 GB - 100 GB	12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Process feasibility - data elaboration	Elaboration of data from process simulation	Research data and metadata	M1-6	MW	-	Partner server	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Process feasibility - data presentation	Prefeasibility with proposed steel grades	Research data and metadata	M1-6	MW	-	Partner server	.pptx, .pdf	Powerpoint	< 10MB	12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Case studies definition analysis	Evaluate pro and cons of MW products to identify the	Research data and metadata	M1	MW	-	Partner server	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	15	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an	10 years	N/A

			best case study											IPR strategy		
WP1	Created	An Overview of Aluminium Automotive Alloy Metallurgy and Considerations for the Fatigue4Light project	Critical review of parameters affecting aluminium alloy and performance for automotive applications	Research data and metadata	M6	Profilglas	-	Partner server	.pdf	adobe creator	8 MB	13	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Preliminary weight reduction target assessment - simulation	Evaluate the weight reduction potential for the possible case studies	Research data and metadata	M3-6	MW	-	Partner server	.st7 (and related process files .lsl, .lsa, .dat, .nas, etc.)	Strauss	100 MB - 500 MB	15	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Preliminary weight reduction target assessment - elaboration	Evaluate the weight reduction potential for the possible case studies	Research data and metadata	M3-6	MW	-	Partner server	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	15	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A

WP1	Created	Stamping simulations to define prototypes configuration	Stamping simulations to define stamping cycle and tooling modifications for prototype production in WP6	Research data and metadata	M4-6	MW	Arcelor Mittal (material cards)	Partner server	.psp (and related process files .asw, .att, .res, .his, etc.)	ESI pam-stamp	10 GB - 100 GB	1	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Tools 3D models	Cad Models of tooling to allow HSS stamping cycles of prototypes	Research data and metadata	M4-6	MW	-	Partner server	.prt (and related process files .stp, .igs, .fem, etc.)	UG NX	10 MB - 100 MB	1	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Fracture Toughness	Material performance/characterization	Research data and metadata	M15	EUT	AMMR, Profilglas, RISE, UPC, GES	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel	< 100MB	3	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Rapid Fatigue test	Material performance/characterization	Research data and metadata	M15	EUT	AMMR, Profilglas, RISE, UPC, GES	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel	< 100MB	4,5,6	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	Fatigue resistance	Material performance	Research data and metadata	M15	EUT	AMMR, Profilglas	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel + pdf + txt	< 100MB	4,5,6	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible	10 years	N/A

		e, SN curve	ce/characterization	metadata			s, RISE, UPC, GES							le to be protected by an IPR strategy		
WP1	Created	D1.1. Methodological framework to support integrated eco-design for EV	Report on Deliverable 1.1.	Documents and dissemination materials	M15	EUT	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	D1.2 Eco-design of Fatigue4Light materials	Report on Deliverable 1.2	Documents and dissemination materials	M15	EUT	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIRE
WP1	Created	D1.3. Selection and definition of lab-scale and industrial demonstrator	Report on Deliverable 1.3	Documents and dissemination materials	M6	CRF	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	D1.4. Lightweight materials selection	Report on Deliverable 1.4	Documents and dissemination materials	M15	EUT	EUT, RISE, AMMR	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIRE

WP1	collected	20210215_FATIGUE4LIGHT_NP_STEEL_LCA_MECHANICAL_CONSTRAINTS 2	CAD files of the hybrid LCA	Research data and metadata	M2	RISE	CRF	sharepoint	step	CAD software	80 MB	10,11,14	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	collected	20210215_FATIGUE4LIGHT_NP_STEEL_LCA_MECHANICAL_CONSTRAINTS	CAD files of the LCA	Research data and metadata	M2	CRF	CRF	sharepoint	step	CAD software	80 MB	12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	collected	20210324_LCA_CAE_LOADS	load description to be applied on LCA	Research data and metadata	M2	CRF	CRF	sharepoint	pdf	adobe creator	240 KB	12,13,14	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	collected	20210216_Assembly Constraints_NP_information 1	description of hybrid LCA parts	Research data and metadata	M2	RISE	CRF	sharepoint	ppt	power point	2 MB	11,13,14	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	collected	20210216_Assembly Constraints	description of LCA parts	Research data and metadata	M2	CRF	CRF	sharepoint	ppt	power point	2 MB	12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected	10 years	N/A

WP1	created	LCA_inventory	Material/pr oduction data regarding for LCA	Research data and metada ta	M7	RISE	RISE, CRF	sharepoi nt	xlsx	xlsx	25 kB		Confiden tial	Related to a KER susceptib le to be protecte d by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP1	Created	An Overview of Aluminium Automotive Alloy Metallurgy and Considerations for the Fatigue4Light project	Critical review of parameters affecting aluminium alloy and performance for automotive applications	Research data and metada ta	M6	Profilglas s	-	Partner server	.pdf	adobe creator	8 MB	13	Confiden tial	Related to a KER susceptib le to be protecte d by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP2	Created	Rapid Fatigue testing by damage control	Methodolo gy of the developed advanced fatigue testing methodolo gies	Research data and metada ta	M7	EUT	AMMR, LTU, RISE, UPC	Sharepoi nt	.docx	Word	< 10MB	5	Public	N/A	N/A	OPENAIR E
WP2	Created	Rapid Fatigue testing by damage control	Results of the developed advanced fatigue testing	Research data and metada ta	M7	EUT	AMMR, LTU, RISE, UPC	Sharepoi nt	.docx	Word	< 10MB	5	Confiden tial	Related to a KER susceptib le to be protecte d by an	10 years	N/A

			methodologies											IPR strategy		
WP2	Created	Accelerated fatigue tests	Material performance/characterization	Research data and metadata	M14	POLITO	POLITO	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	6	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP2	Created	Advanced statistical treatment	Material performance/characterization	Research data and metadata	M17	POLITO	POLITO	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	7	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP2	Created	D2.1 Advanced fatigue testing methods	Report on Deliverable 2.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M7	AMMR	EUT, CRF, POLITO, RISE, UPC	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	1,2	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP3	Created	Fatigue Simulation	Model development	Research data and metadata	M7	CIMNE		Sharepoint	.txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiphysics, GiD, Visual Studio	>10MB	2	Public	N/A	N/A	OPENAIRE
WP3	Created	Fatigue Simulation	Comparison with current	Research data and	M7	CIMNE	CRF, GES	Sharepoint	.txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos	>10MB	2	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be	10 years	N/A

			software for metals	metada ta						Multiply sics, GiD, Visual Studio					protecte d by an IPR strategy		
WP3	Created	Fatigue Simulation	Calibration of material parameters for the simulation of the metals used in the project	Resear ch data and metada ta	M8	CIMNE	CRF, GES, EUT, AMMR	Sharepoi nt	.txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiply sics, GiD, Visual Studio	> 10MB	2	Confiden tial	Related to a KER susceptib le to be protecte d by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A	
WP3	Created	Fatigue Simulation	Calibration and validation of the fatigue model for composites	Resear ch data and metada ta	M15	CIMNE	CRF, RISE	Sharepoi nt	.txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiply sics, GiD, Visual Studio	> 10MB	2	Confiden tial	Related to a KER susceptib le to be protecte d by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A	
WP3	Created	Validatio n on small scale specimen s	Fatigue tests for load sequence effect, residual life and overload effect	Resear ch data and metada ta	M18	EUT	CIMNE, CRF, GES, RISE, UPC	Sharepoi nt	.txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Excel, Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiply sics, GiD, Visual Studio	< 10MB	5	Confiden tial	Related to a KER susceptib le to be protecte d by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A	
WP 3	created	F4L_Fatig ue modellin g approach _2021-12-13.pptx	Fatigue Modeling Composite s Presentation	Docum ents and dissemin ation materia ls	M11	RISE	CIMNE, CRF	sharepoi nt	pptx	PowerPoi nt	< 10MB	2	Public	N/A	N/A	Self- archive on website + OPENAIR E repository	

WP 3	created	F4L_GLARE_2021-11-05.pptx	Modeling of GLARE Presentation	Documents and dissemination materials	M4	CIMNE	RISE, CRF	sharepoint	pptx	PowerPoint	< 10MB	1,2	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP 3	created	F4L_Kratos-constitutive-models_2021-11-05.pptx	Constitutive Models Kratos Presentation	Documents and dissemination materials	M4	CIMNE	RISE, CRF	sharepoint	pptx	PowerPoint	< 10MB	1,2	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP 3	created	Overview Literature.xlsx	Literature	Research data and metadata	M11	RISE	RISE, CIMNE, CRF	sharepoint	xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	1,2	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP 3	created	Overview Software Solutions .xlsx	Software	Computer Software	M11	RISE	RISE, CIMNE, CRF	sharepoint	xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	1,2	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP3	Created	D3.1. Numerical analyses of steel/multi-	Report on Deliverable 3.1	Documents and dissemination	M18	CIMNE	EUT, CRF, LTU, AMMR, GES, RISE, UPC	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	1,2	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A

		materials solution		materials												
WP4	Created	Fatigue test of bent specimen	Evaluate the effect of forming and shot peening on fatigue	Research data and metadata	M9	MW	Arcelor Mittal (steel supply)	Partner server	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	9,12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP4	Created	Effect of forming	Fatigue tests on pre-strained specimens	Research data and metadata	M20	EUT	RISE, AMMR, UPC, Profilglas, MW	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	9	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP4	Created	Effect of welding	Fatigue tests on welded specimens	Research data and metadata	M24	EUT	LTU, AMMR, CRF	Sharepoint	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	9	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP4	Created	Fatigue Simulation	Enhancement of the fatigue model to account for cutting, welding and forming effects	Research data and metadata	M24	CIMNE	CIMNE, LTU, AMM, CRF, MW	Sharepoint	.xlsx, .txt, .json, .mdpa, .docs, .post.bin	Excel, Word, Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiphysics, GiD, Visual Studio	> 10MB	2	Public	N/A	N/A	OPENAIRE repository

WP4	Created	D4.1 Experimental and numerical results on forming effects	Report on Deliverable 4.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M24	LTU	CIMNE, EUT, CRF, MW, AMMR, POLITO, RISE, Profilglas, UPC	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	2,9	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP5	Created	Acoustic emission sensors	Monitoring of damage evolution	Research data and metadata	M24	EUT	RISE	Sharepoint	.xlsx, .docx	Excel, Word	> 10MB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	OPENAIR E repository
WP5	created	WP5 State-of-the-art fibre optic strain sensors	Report	Documents and dissemination materials	M14	RISE	RISE	sharepoint	docx	Word	20MB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP5	created	Part performance monitoring	Status Report	Documents and dissemination materials	M18	RISE	RISE, EUT	sharepoint	pptx	Powerpoint	3MB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP5	created	Health monitoring Techniques, chassies parts	Method descriptions	Documents and dissemination materials	M24	RISE	RISE, EUT	sharepoint	pptx	Powerpoint	4,3MB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository

WP5	created	D5.1 Health monitoring techniques for chassis parts	Report on Deliverable 5.1	Documents and dissemination materials	44957	RISE	RISE, EUT	sharepoint	docx	Word	5,8MB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP5	created	Embedding fiber optical sensors in FRP-Hybrid material	Dissemination	Documents and dissemination materials	May 2023	RISE	RISE	project website and partner service	PDF	Word	775kB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP5	created	D5.1 Health monitoring techniques for chassis parts	Report on Deliverable 5.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M24	RISE	RISE, EUT	sharepoint	docx	Word	MB	16	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP6	Created	D6.1 Life cycle assessment and recycling options of Fatigue4Light solutions	Report on Deliverable 6.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M27	EUT	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository

WP6	Created	D6.2 Eco-design of Fatigue4Light chassis parts	Report on Deliverable 6.2	Documents and dissemination materials	M27	EUT	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP6	Created	D6.3. Fatigue behaviour of lab-scale demonstrator	Report on Deliverable 6.3	Documents and dissemination materials	M27	EUT	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP6	Created	Tools Cad drawings	Drawings of the tooling to be manufactured for prototypes construction	Research data and metadata	M13-16	MW	-	Partner server	.e3 (and related process file .dwg .dxf .pdf)	Think Design	10 MB - 100 MB	9,12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP6	Created	Prototypes production reports	Report on prototyping activities	Research data and metadata	M16-M24	MW	Arcelor Mittal (steel supply)	Partner server	.docx .pptx	Word / Powerpoint	< 10MB	9,12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP6	Created	Fatigue test on prototypes	Evaluate the fatigue performance of prototypes	Research data and metadata	M19-27	MW	-	Partner server	.xlsx .docx	Excel / Word	< 10MB	9,12	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A

WP6	created	LCA hybrid final	Final FE simulation of hybrid LCA	Research data and metadata	M19-27	RISE	RISE	Partner server	db	ansys	1.5 GB	3	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIR E repository
WP6	created	LCA forming analyses	FE simulation of forming aluminium sheets	Research data and metadata	M19-27	RISE	RISE	Partner server	.k	ls dyna	1.5 GB	3	Public	N/A	N/A	OPENAIR E repository
WP6	created	Tools Cad drawings	Drawings of the tooling to be manufactured for prototypes construction	Research data and metadata	M19-27	RISE	RISE	Partner server	.sldprt	solid works	7 MB	3	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP6	Created	Deliverable MW contribution	MW contribution in WP6 deliverable (Prototypes production & testing)	Documents and dissemination materials	M19-27	MW	-	Partner server	.docx .pptx	Word / Powerpoint	< 10MB	9,12	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP6	Created	Lab-scale demonstrator	Fatigue tests and numerical simulation on lab scale demonstrator	Research data and metadata	M27	EUT	POLITO, CIMNE, MW	Sharepoint	.xlsx, .txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Excel, Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiphysics, GiD, Visual Studio	> 10MB	9	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A

WP7	Created	Lower control arm demonstrator	Fatigue tests and numerical simulation on demonstrator	Research data and metadata	M33	CRF	CIMNE, CSE, RISE	Sharepoint	.xlsx, .txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin, .word, .ppt	Excel, Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiphysics, GiD, Visual Studio, power point, word	> 10MB	8	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP7	Created	Cross-member beam demonstrator	Fatigue tests and numerical simulation on demonstrator	Research data and metadata	M33	GES	CRF, CIMNE, EUT	Sharepoint	.xlsx, .txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Excel, Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiphysics, GiD, Visual Studio	> 10MB	3	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP7	Created	Simulation on wheel, LCA and cross-member beam prototype	Numerical simulation on prototype	Research data and metadata	M33	CIMNE	CRF, MW, RISE, GES	Sharepoint	.xlsx, .txt, .json, .mdpa, .post.bin	Excel, Notepad, Text Editors, Kratos Multiphysics, GiD, Visual Studio	> 10MB	1,2	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP7	Created	Wheel 3D models	3D Models of prototypes and final virtual demonstrator	Research data and metadata	M22-30	MW	-	Partner server	.prt (and related process files .stp, .igs, .fem, etc.)	UG NX	10 MB - 100 MB	15	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A

WP7	Created	Final demonstrator simulations	Correlate calculation on prototypes and simulate final demonstrator	Research data and metadata	M22-33	MW	CIMNE	Partner server	.st7 (and related process files .lsl, .lsa, .dat, .nas, etc.)	Strauss	100 MB - 500 MB	8	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP7	Created	Simulation data elaboration	Elaborate the results of fatigue simulations	Research data and metadata	M22-33	MW	CIMNE	Partner server	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	9	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be protected by an IPR strategy	10 years	N/A
WP7	Created	D7.1. Virtual testing on LDEV and HDV parts and EV wheels	Report on Deliverable 7.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M33	CRF	CIMNE, GES, CSE, EUT, MW	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	8,9	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP8	Created	D8.1. Lightweight potential and performance the solutions analysed	Report on Deliverable 8.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M36	CIMNE	EUT, RISE, CRF, MW, GES	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP8	Created	Comparison from different wheel kpi	Elaborate and balance weighth	Research data and	M31-36	MW	CIMNE, EUT	Partner server	.xlsx	Excel	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Related to a KER susceptible to be	10 years	N/A

			reduction in comparison to other kpi	metada ta										protected by an IPR strategy		
WP9	Created	D9.1. Project Quality Plan (quality, risk, change management)	Report on Deliverable 9.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M2	CIMNE	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	3	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP9	Created	D9.2. Gender Equity Policy	Report on Deliverable 9.2	Documents and dissemination materials	M2	CIMNE	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	4	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP9	Created	D9.3. Project Management Plan	Report on Deliverable 9.3	Documents and dissemination materials	M3	CIMNE	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	5	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP9	Created	D9.4. Project Management Plan - update 1	Report on Deliverable 9.4	Documents and dissemination materials	M17	CIMNE	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	6	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP9	Created	D9.5. Project Manage	Report on Deliverable 9.5	Documents and	M35	CIMNE	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe	< 10MB	7	Confidential	Confidential	10 years	N/A

		ment Plan - update 2		dissemination materials						Acrobat for pdf				deliverable		
WP10	Created	D10.1. Project launch and Communication and Dissemination Plan	Report on Deliverable 10.1	Documents and dissemination materials	M3	EUT	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	N/A	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP10	Created	D10.2. Initial Data Management Plan	Report on Deliverable 10.2	Documents and dissemination materials	M6	EUT	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	N/A	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP10	Created	D10.3 Relevant standardization landscape and applicable standards	Report on Deliverable 10.3	Documents and dissemination materials	M6	EUT	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	N/A	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A
WP10	Created	D10.4. Interim plan of Use and Dissemination of Results	Report on Deliverable 10.4	Documents and dissemination materials	M3, with updated at M18	EUT	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	< 10MB	N/A	Confidential	Confidential deliverable	10 years	N/A

WP10	Created	D10.5. Final Plan of Use and Dissemination of Results and Communication Activities - PUDR	Report on Deliverable 10.5	Documents and dissemination materials	M1, with updates at M18 and M36	EUT	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	Word, Excel	10MB	N/A	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIRE repository
WP10	Created	D10.6. Report on the contribution to standardization	Report on Deliverable 10.6	Documents and dissemination materials	M9 with updates at M18 and M36	UNE	All	Fatigue4Light's Sharepoint and webpage	.docx .pdf	MS Word, Adobe Acrobat for pdf	10MB	N/A	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIRE repository
WP10	Created	D10.7 Final Data Management Plan	Report on Deliverable 10.7	Documents and dissemination materials	M3, with updates at M18 and M36	EUT	All	Sharepoint	.docx .pdf	Word	< 10MB	N/A	Public	N/A	N/A	Self-archive on website + OPENAIRE repository